

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF IBN SINA'S
PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS

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Abstract: The article talks about the philosophical views in Ibn Sina's work and the history of their study. The author Ibn Sina tried to illuminate the philosophical essence of his works written in the fields of philosophy, nature, medicine and fiction, as well as music.

Keywords: Philosophy, medicine, music, science, culture

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A part of Ibn Sina's scientific and creative activity was spent in Isfahan and Hamadan. He lived in the city of Hamadan from 1014 until the end of his life and was directly connected with the scientific, cultural and literary environment of this place.[1.1.10-b]

The great philosopher-scientist Ibn Sina wrote many works in the field of philosophy, nature, medicine and other sciences. Ibn Sina lived in almost all of the above-mentioned cities and undoubtedly got acquainted with the literary life and communicated with poets, philosophers and scientists. An in-depth study of Ibn Sina's philosophical heritage will clarify this issue.

Method and the main part: It is written in scientific and philosophical sources that Samani rulers valued knowledge, enlightenment, philosophers and scholars and patronized them. Nizami Aruzi Samarkandi, a scientist who lived after Ibn Sina and the secretary of Ghurian kings, writes in his work "Majmui-nawadir yahud chohar qaharan": "Nasr ibn Ahmad was a masterpiece of scholars belonging to the Samanid dynasty. The prosperity of this house coincided with the period of his reign, the means of power were in the period of the kingship and the

prosperity was extremely increased, the treasure was abundant, the army was warlike. The ruler Nasr ibn Ahmad spent the winter in the city of Bukhara, and in the summer he went to one of the cities of Samarkand or Khurasan [2.3.32-b]. During the prosperity of the Samanid state, in Balkh, Nishapur, Bust, Isfahan, Marv and other cities, which were considered the capitals of most regions in Movarunnahr and Khorasan, the emirs subordinate to Bukhara gathered around them philosophers, scientists, enlightened people, and people of talent, and lived an active cultural life. Among them, powerful emirs such as Abu Ali Simjur, Alp Tegin, Fayiq, Sabuntagin also patronized representatives of science.

The fact that these intellectuals who lived in the era of Khorezmshahs, Samonids and Ghaznavids were also military commanders, philosophers, poets, geographers, physicians and astrologers are signs and symbols of the humanism of the Eastern Renaissance.

Philosophers who worked on negative and critical topics during the Somanids and Ghaznavid eras, the talent and creativity of representatives of fiction and literature were respected, and although they criticized the representatives of the government, the prime minister promoted them to high positions. In one of his poems, the poet Abu Ahmed, who is famous in literature and ethics, criticizes the minister Jaihani saying that he is not even fit to be a guard. Nevertheless, considering his abilities, he was appointed governor of the region.

Ibn Sina, a young philosopher and scientist, grew up in such a social and cultural environment. For example, in his autobiography, Ibn Sina says the following about his youth and formation as a philosopher:

"Then we moved to the city of Bukhara (from Afshona). They handed me over to teachers who teach the Qur'an and etiquette. By the time I was ten years old, I had mastered the Qur'an and most of the literature. Even people were surprised by me. My father was one of those who accepted the call of the Egyptians and was considered one of the Ismailis, and I used to listen to their words and concepts about the soul and mind, and so did my brother. Often when

they were talking about this, I understood what they were saying, but my heart did not accept it" [4.1.62.].

According to historical data, the origin of the Ismaili doctrine is related to the recognition of Musa al-Kazim (d. 799), the son of Ja'far Sadiq from Hazrat Ali's generation, as the seventh imam. Another group of Shia sects of Islam recognized Ismail, the eldest son of Ja'far Sadiq, as the seventh imam.

Since Imam Ismail died before his father, his son Muhammad ibn Ismail was recognized as the seventh Imam-Rahbar. The supporters of Musa al-Kazim began to call themselves Imamis, and the supporters of Muhammad ibn Ismail began to call themselves Ismailis.

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